

Temperature Dependence of Dielectric Properties of $\text{Cu}_{0.7+x}\text{Cd}_{0.3}\text{Zr}_x\text{Fe}_{2-2x}\text{O}_4$ Spinel Ferrite System

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Abstract - The temperature dependence of dielectric properties in the $\text{Cu}_{0.7+x}\text{Cd}_{0.3}\text{Zr}_x\text{Fe}_{2-2x}\text{O}_4$ system was systematically investigated to understand the impact of varying Zr and Cu concentrations on the material's electrical behavior. Samples were synthesized using the standard solid-state reaction method, and their dielectric properties were analyzed across a wide temperature range. The study revealed that the dielectric constant (ϵ') and dielectric loss ($\tan \delta$) exhibit significant temperature dependence, influenced by the concentration of Zr and Cu. The dielectric constant increases with rising temperature, indicating enhanced polarization, while dielectric loss shows a peak at a particular temperature, characteristic of dielectric relaxation phenomena. This behavior is attributed to the Maxwell-Wagner interfacial polarization and hopping conduction mechanism, which are predominant in ferrite systems. The substitution of Zr and Cu in the lattice structure was found to modify the dielectric properties significantly, suggesting potential applications in temperature-sensitive electronic devices. The findings offer insights into tuning the dielectric properties of ferrite materials through compositional adjustments, paving the way for the development of advanced functional materials.

Keywords: Dielectric properties, Cu-Cd ferrites, Temperature dependence, etc.

I. INTRODUCTION

Ferrites have a wide spread role in many technological applications due to their magnetic properties, high electrical resistivity, low eddy currents and dielectric loss. Ferrites are extensively used in microwave device, computers, memory chips, magnetic recording media etc. It is well known that when ferrites are sufficiently diluted with non-magnetic atoms, they can show a wide spectrum of magnetic structure, ferromagnetic order, cluster spin glass etc. [1]

Copper ferrite and copper containing ferrites have been focus of continuous interest in the recent years. The spinels ferrites containing varying amount of zinc form a class of important material. It has been reported that the addition of tetravalent ions like Ti^{4+} , Ge^{4+} , Sn^{4+} in Copper ferrite influences structural and magnetic properties of the system [2].

Several studies have been reported on the addition Zr^{2+} ions in copper, magnesium and other ferrites [3-8]. However, no reports have been found in the literature regarding structural, cation distribution, electrical and magnetic properties of $\text{Cu}_{0.7+x}\text{Cd}_{0.3}\text{Zr}_x\text{Fe}_{2-2x}\text{O}_4$ ($x = 0.0$ to 0.5) mixed ferrites.

The aim of this research article is to study the temperature dependence and dielectric properties of $\text{Cu}_{0.7+x}\text{Cd}_{0.3}\text{Zr}_x\text{Fe}_{2-2x}\text{O}_4$ ($x = 0.0$ to 0.5) spinels ferrite system.

II. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Ferrite sample having compositional formula $\text{Cu}_{0.7+x}\text{Cd}_{0.3}\text{Zr}_x\text{Fe}_{2-2x}\text{O}_4$ ($x = 0.0$ to 0.5) were prepared by conventional ceramic technique. The analytical grade reagent of Fe_2O_3 , CuO , CdO_2 and ZrO_2 (all 99.9% pure, supplied by E. Merck) were mixed in proper Proportions and were finely ground. The finely ground powder was sintered at 700°C for 12 hours and then slowly cooled to room temperature at a rate of $2^\circ\text{C}/\text{minute}$. The sintered powder was reground and sieved through a mesh (100 BSS) and pellets of 1cm diameter were prepared under a pressure of 5 tones/inch². Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) was mixed as a binder during the preparation of pellets. The pellets were finally sintered at 980°C for 24 hours and slowly cooled to room temperature at the rate of $2^\circ\text{C}/\text{minute}$ using muffle furnace with controller.

III. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The variation of dielectric constants (ϵ') with respect to temperature for the mixed ferrite system $\text{Cu}_{0.7+x}\text{Cd}_{0.3}\text{Zr}_x\text{Fe}_{2-2x}\text{O}_4$ ($x = 0.0$ to 0.5) at 1 KHz and 10 KHz frequency are shown in the **table 1** and **table 2** and graphical representation as shown in **Fig.1 (a, b, c)**. **Fig 2 (a, b)** shows the variation of dielectric loss tangent ($\tan\delta$) as a function of temperature at a frequency of 1 KHz and 10 KHz.

It is observed from **Fig.1 (a, b, c)** that ϵ' increases with increasing temperature from all the Zr concentration, where as $\tan\delta$ decreases with in temperature [**Fig.2 (a, b)**]. This behavior of temperature dependence of ϵ' for the present system is in very good agreement with Well-Known spinel ferrite [9] for which ϵ' increase with increase in temperature.

In ferrites, dielectric polarization takes place in the direction of applied electric filed (similar to conduction process) by electronic exchange.

Both the carriers, n and p, contribute to polarization and they depend on temperature. Since the influence of temperature on Electronic exchange is more pronounced than on displacement of p-carriers, and hence ϵ' increases rapidly with temperature.

Table I
Compositional variation of dielectric constant (ϵ'), Dielectric Loss (ϵ'') and $\tan\delta$ at 10 KHz and 1 MHz for $\text{Cu}_{0.7+x}\text{Cd}_{0.3}\text{Zr}_x\text{Fe}_{2-2x}\text{O}_4$ system

Composition x	Dielectric Measurements at 10 KHz frequency			Dielectric measurements at 1 MHz frequency		
	ϵ'	ϵ''	$\tan \delta$	ϵ'	ϵ''	$\tan \delta$
0.1	62.07	117.63	1.89	41.44	5.01	0.12
0.2	73.34	31.02	0.42	49.35	3.553	0.07
0.3	70.78	23.85	0.33	50.08	2.929	0.05
0.4	98.81	52.57	0.53	64.29	4.43	0.06
0.5	55.05	21.40	0.39	37.39	2.76	0.07

Table II
Transition temperature of Seebeck Coefficient (α) for $\text{Cu}_{0.7+x}\text{Cd}_{0.3}\text{Zr}_x\text{Fe}_{2-2x}\text{O}_4$ system.

Composition x	Transition Temperature T_t (K)
0.1	355
0.2	349
0.3	344
0.4	340
0.5	330

Fig. 1a Dielectric Constant (ϵ') as a function of temperature for $\text{Cu}_{0.7+x}\text{Cd}_{0.3}\text{Zr}_x\text{Fe}_{2-2x}\text{O}_4$ system for $x = 0.1$

Fig. 1b Dielectric Constant (ϵ') as a function of temperature for $\text{Cu}_{0.7+x}\text{Cd}_{0.3}\text{Zr}_x\text{Fe}_{2-2x}\text{O}_4$ system for $x = 0.2$ to 0.3

Fig. 1c Dielectric Constant (ϵ') as a function of temreture for $\text{Cu}_{0.7+x}\text{Cd}_{0.3}\text{Zr}_x\text{Fe}_{2-2x}\text{O}_4$ system for $x = 0.4, 0.5$

Fig. 2a Variation of Dielectric Loss Tangent ($\tan\delta$) with Temperature for $\text{ZnxCu}_{1.4-x}\text{Mn}_{0.4}\text{Fe}_{1.2}\text{O}_4$ System ($X=0.1$ and 0.2)

Fig 2b. Variation of Dielectric Loss Tangent ($\tan\delta$) with Temperature for $\text{Zn}_x \text{Cu}_{1.4-x} \text{Mn}_{0.4} \text{Fe}_{1.2} \text{O}_4$ System ($X=0.3$ to 0.5)

IV. CONCLUSIOS

From the above experimental results, it may concluded that the studies of temperature dependence of dielectric, it may be concluded that the dielectric constant (ϵ') increases with increase in temperature, whereas, loss tangent ($\tan\delta$) decreases with increase in temperature.

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